

MiniLiVE: miniaturized light- and video-unit for a wireless and networkable medical video endoscope

Horim Bae¹, Mike Fornefett^{2*}

¹ *Universitätsmedizin Göttingen, Institut für Medizininformatik, Göttingen, Germany*
email: horim.bae@uni-med.goettingen.de

² *Industrial Technologies Department, Furtwangen University, Tuttlingen, Germany*
email: mike.fornefett@hs-furtwangen.de

Abstract: Recently, video endoscopes have become the standard technology and already convey high quality images on monitors in the operation room. Nevertheless, the large-sized and relatively heavy-weighted hand piece and electric cables existing between the control unit and the endoscope disturb the physician's freedom of movement. To overcome these drawbacks and bring an innovation to the endoscope, miniLiVE research team conducted research on the miniaturized light- and video unit for a wireless video transmission. During a two-year research project, miniLiVE research team developed an executable prototype for the examination of the upper trachea, esophagus, and nasal cavity.

© Copyright 2024

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License CC-BY 4.0., which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

I. Introduction

In the last few years, video endoscopes have become the standard technology, and it allows physicians to observe ever-changing surgical situations on multiple monitors in the operating room by delivering high-quality images to multiple monitors. For this purpose, a relatively heavy camera is placed on the hand piece, or a small-sized integrated camera sensor is located on the distal tip of the endoscope, a so-called chip-in-tip-endoscope (CIT). Furthermore, electric cables existing between the control unit and the endoscope are one of the essential components for data transfer from the endoscope and supplying power to the endoscope. In addition to electric cables, the control unit contains a light source, which generates light and delivers it to the endoscope over fiber optic cables. In this way, it can prevent patients and physicians from being damaged, due to incidental heats. Despite these advantages of video endoscopes, the large-sized and relatively heavy-weighted hand piece of endoscopes and electrical cables connected to the endoscope for power supply and conveyance of data restrict the freedom of physicians' movement. This is where miniLiVE research project comes to overcome these drawbacks and bring an innovation to the endoscope. In this context, miniLiVE stands for the miniaturized light- and video- unit for a wireless and networkable medical video endoscope, and CoHMed (Connected Health in Medical Mountain) supports the research project "miniLiVE" (CoHMed [2], Bae H. R. and Fornefett M. [1])

I.1. miniLiVE research team and plan

Our research team is composed of Furtwangen University (HFU), Kiehn Engineering Services GmbH (K.E.S), and

EMOS Technology GmbH, and the research team aims to realize all aspects of endoscope wirelessly, addressing the following topics: wireless, miniaturization of the endoscope, and network capability. In the development process, our research team have encountered eight challenges and addressed them during our two-year CoHMed project. To produce a wireless video endoscope, a cordless endoscope will replace electric cables and these systems encompass a LED light source, a battery system with charging coils, and associated electronics for data transmission.

MiniLiVE: Challenges

Figure 1: Challenges in miniLiVE research project. It demonstrates existing eight challenges, and they can be divided into three sections: device (EMOS), hardware (K.E.S), and software (HFU)

II. Method

II.1. Device: mechanical construction

In incorporating the wireless endoscope systems into the hand piece, a CMOS camera sensor is integrated into the distal tip of the endoscope and an additional housing was added under the hand piece, which encompasses LED light source, batteries, and electronics (Fig 2). To handle heat-

related issues from the miniaturized video sensor unit, EMOS has conducted some experiments to select a suitable material for cooling variants and determine a proper place to put the material in the hand piece. In terms of the endoscope tip, the mechanics enable the endoscope tip to be bendable, and using light guides, EMOS integrates sensors on the endoscope tip and these light guides would surround the sensors. Thereby, the integrated sensors are encased firmly and tightly.

Device: Construction of the Prototype

Figure 2: Construction of the prototype. Under the hand piece, additional housing is constructed where the electronics with charging coils are placed. Thereby, the batteries can be charged with a charging tray

II.II. Electronics: electronics Developments

The video unit consisting of an FPGA and a microcontroller realizes the integration of sensors at the tip of the endoscope, and two lithium-ion batteries power all electronics for approximately 2,5 hours of operation (Fig 3).

Figure 3: FPGA and microcontroller with lithium-ion batteries. Lithium-ion batteries power all electronics, and the FPGA handles A/D conversion, image compression, and data transfer.

In terms of coding of video data and data transmission, image data from the camera sensor on the distal tip are forwarded to the electronics via channels. Following this, the data processing procedures programmed with FPGA take place.

II.III. Software: Software development

To implement client software, while fulfilling the user's perspectives, understanding the usage context of the endoscope is crucial. In the context of miniLiVE research project, 90-120 minutes contextual interview with users were conducted to analyze the usage contexts, and each interview is based on a master-apprentice model. In the course of the usage context analysis, a total of five contextual interviews were conducted, and 124 requirements were derived from the contextual scenarios.

With client software (receiving software), the users can establish a maximum 1,5m Wi-Fi connection between the endoscope and client software. In terms of latency, the research team initially aimed to reach less than 200ms latency. Nevertheless, it took steadily 200-250ms latency from data acquisition to presenting incoming video streaming with UI-SW (Fig 4).

III. Results and discussion

During the two-year research project, miniLiVE research team developed an executable prototype with integrated sensors, miniaturized associated electronics, and client software for the examination of the upper trachea, esophagus, and nasal cavity (Fig 4, 5).

Figure 4: UI for user test (formative testing) in Tübingen. The user can control the Wi-Fi connection and observe the live view.

Figure 5: MiniLiVE endoscope in its latest development version. The current version of the hand piece.

In terms of the endoscope, the endoscope tip can be deflectable up to 160° and the users can utilize the developed prototype either as a flexible endoscope or as a rigid endoscope by mounting an additional attachment to the endoscope tip. The receiving station would retrieve incoming video data with 400 × 400 resolution from the sensor via video unit over Wi-Fi and display it with maximum 900 × 900 resolution on an external monitor within 200ms latency. In the end, usage scenarios were tailored to wireless endoscope systems and a formative user test was conducted on body models in collaboration with the University Hospital of Tübingen.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank the interview partners, the students who wrote their thesis related to the project and the Institute for Experimental Endoscopy, Development and Training at the University of Tübingen for the formative evaluation, in particular Dr. Wichmann and Dr. Duckworth-Mothes.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

This research was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research as part of the "Forschung an Fachhochschulen" funding program under contract number 13FH5E04IA (CoHMed / miniLiVE project). Conflict of interest: Authors state no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Horim Bae, Mike Fomefett: MiniLiVE: miniaturized light- and video-unit for a wireless and networkable medical video endoscope, in: Balázs Benyó (ed.): IFAC-PapersOnLine, Volume 58, Issue 24, 2024, Pages 397-402, ISSN 2405-8963, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2405-8963\(24\)02239-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2405-8963(24)02239-0)
- [2] CoHMed. (n.d.). Retrieved September 29, 2022, from <https://cohm-ed.hs-furtwangen.de/ueber-cohmed/>